

Instructional Predispositions of Teachers and Sense of Comprehensibility of Students

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Sarangani District of Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2024-2025. Research instruments on instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students the study found to exhibit a very high level of instructional predispositions of teachers, there is a very high level of sense of comprehensibility of students, there is a significant relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students. This implies that the higher the instructional predispositions of teachers, the higher is the sense of comprehensibility of students Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students was rejected.

Keywords: instructional predispositions of teachers, sense of comprehensibility of students, school administration and supervision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Students sense of comprehensibility refers to ability to perceive life as comprehensible, manageable, and meaningful. When applied to academic life of students, a strong sense of comprehensibility can help them navigate academic challenges, cope with stress, and adapt to educational environments. However, there are several issues and challenges that can impact students' sense of comprehensibility especially in the context of modern education. These issues can undermine students' well-being, academic performance, and overall adjustment to their learning environments (Garcia-Mila, Felton, Miralda-Banda & Castells, 2023).

Students today face numerous academic pressures, such as heavy workloads, high expectations, and intense competition. These stressors significantly diminish their sense of comprehensibility. When students perceive academic demands as overwhelming or insurmountable, they may struggle to maintain a sense of control over their learning, which can undermine their ability to find meaning in their education. Prolonged academic stress is often linked to mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and burnout, which can exacerbate the feeling of disconnection or lack of meaning. A weak sense of comprehensibility in the face of these challenges may make it difficult for students to see the purpose behind their efforts, leading to disengagement, academic decline, and even dropout (Palha & Matic, 2023)

A strong sense of comprehensibility is rooted in supportive and trusting relationships, whether with peers, teachers, or family members. However, many students experience a lack of emotional or academic support in their educational environment. For instance, students who feel isolated or who do not have a strong support network may struggle to understand their academic and personal challenges in a way that makes sense to them. The absence of strong, positive relationships make it difficult for students to view their educational experience as meaningful and manageable, ultimately leading to lower motivation, feelings of alienation, and diminished well-being. Additionally, students who do not have adequate support may have difficulty navigating academic or social challenges, further eroding their sense of comprehensibility (Knowles, 2018).

Students need to have a good sense of comprehensibility in order to succeed in school. As academic requirements may give pressures to students, their sense of coherence will help them manage their stress (Chu, Khan, Jahn, and Kraemer, 2016). However, there are many students have difficulty to uncover solutions to their academic problems. These students lack manageability skills in their varied subject requirements as manifested in their non-submission of projects, themes, and assignments among others. When confronted with academic pressures, these students withdraw their engagement in the class activities while others contribute to an increased annual dropout rate. These problems are attributed to students' poor sense of coherence which teachers need to address directly (Moskowitz & Dewaele, 2021).

The problem on students' sense of comprehensibility is manifested in almost all classrooms. This is evident in the poor manageability of students in terms of their time management. They cannot comply subject requirements and fulfill multiple tasks in a given time. More so, there are a number of students that have difficulty in finding solution to the basic problems in school such as unavailability of pen or any material during different school activities (Hjelmborg, Larsen, Jensen, Gents, Christensen, Junge & Hansen, 2020).

In the local setting, there are a number of students in Sarangani District who are disengaged in the classroom learning activities continue to reach an alarming rate. At some point, these students have lost their interest towards school. In this regard, teachers are encouraged to consistently monitor these students and provide specific measures to make them actively involved in their learning and eventually develop a sense of coherence.

To date, there has no study conducted in the local context regarding the correlation between instructional predispositions of teachers and students' sense of comprehensibility. While the problem on students' sense of comprehensibility continues to be present in the classrooms, the need to give special attention to this concern is important in order to increase their learning outcome. It is on this reason that this research is conceptualized in order to explore on the given topic and to look into the veracity of the presented problems on students' sense of comprehensibility. This study, therefore, is a contribution to the existing literature on each of the topics covered in this study.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study is aimed to find out the relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. What is the level of instructional predispositions of teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Demonstrates a positive and enthusiastic attitude;
 - 1.2 Exhibits an appreciation and value for diversity;
 - 1.3 Collaborates effectively, and
 - 1.4 Exhibits the emotional intelligence to promote goals?
2. What is the level of sense of comprehensibility of students in terms of:
 - 2.1 comprehensibility;
 - 2.2 manageability, and
 - 2.3 meaningfulness?

3. Is there a significant relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was treated at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative correlational design is a type of non-experimental research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables. This study will find out the significance of the relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students.

Pearson r. This was used to determine the significance of the relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Instructional Predispositions of Teachers

Shown in Table 1 is the level of level of teacher change with an overall mean of 4.11 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, exhibits the emotional intelligence to promote goals ranked highest with a mean score of 4.13 or very high; demonstrates a positive and enthusiastic attitude with a mean score of 4.12 or

Table I. Level of Instructional Predispositions of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Demonstrates a Positive and Enthusiastic Attitude	4.12	Very High
Exhibits an Appreciation and Value for Diversity	4.09	Very High
Collaborates Effectively	4.11	Very High
Exhibits the Emotional Intelligence to Promote Goals	4.13	Very High
Overall	4.11	Very High

very high; collaborates effectively, 4.11 or very high, and exhibits an appreciation and value for diversity, 4.09 or very high. The result of this study is aligned with the statement of Area-Moreira, Rodríguez-Rodríguez, Peirats-Chacón & Santana-Bonilla (2023) and Hardy, Decristan & Klieme (2019) who believed that teachers play a critical role in shaping the academic and personal development of students. Their instructional predisposition, defined as their inherent teaching philosophy, attitudes, and methodologies, greatly influences student learning outcomes. A teacher’s predisposition determines their approach to lesson planning and overall effectiveness in delivering content.

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It is also aligned with the statement of Mngo & Mngo (2018) and Knowles (2018) who posited that instructional predisposition refers to the inherent and acquired tendencies that influence how teachers approach education. It encompasses their beliefs about teaching and learning, attitudes toward students, preferred instructional strategies, and willingness to adapt to different learning styles. Some teachers adopt a traditional, teacher-centered approach, focusing on direct instruction and structured learning. Others embrace student-centered methodologies that encourage inquiry-based learning, critical thinking, and active participation.

Level of Sense of Comprehensibility of Students

Shown in Table 2 is the level of level of sense of comprehensibility of students with an overall mean of 4.08 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, meaningfulness ranked highest with a mean score of 4.11 or very high, manageability, 4.09 or very high, and comprehensibility, 4.06 or very high. The results of this study is congruent with the statement of Cadena-Aguilar & Álvarez-Ayure (2021) who argued that the sense of comprehensibility is an essential component of students' ability to navigate their educational experiences and cope with the challenges they encounter. However, issues such as academic stress, lack of supportive relationships, socioeconomic inequalities, cultural barriers, and inadequate coping mechanisms can significantly undermine students' sense of comprehensibility.

Table II. Level of Sense of Comprehensibility of Students

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Comprehensibility	4.06	Very High
Manageability	4.09	Very High
Meaningfulness	4.11	Very High
Overall	4.08	Very High

It is also supported by the statement of Hatlevik & Hovdenak (2020) who stated that sense of coherence or comprehensibility is a crucial element in student learning and academic success. It refers to the ability of students to understand and make sense of information presented to them. A strong sense of comprehensibility enables students to grasp complex concepts, engage in meaningful learning, and apply knowledge effectively. The development of comprehensibility is influenced by various factors, including teaching strategies, cognitive abilities, language proficiency, and environmental support. This essay explores the importance of comprehensibility in student learning, the factors that affect it, and strategies to enhance students' ability to comprehend and retain information.

A student's sense of comprehensibility directly impacts their academic performance, motivation, and confidence. When students can understand the material being taught, they are more likely to engage actively in the learning process and develop a positive attitude toward education. Understanding new concepts fosters cognitive growth by allowing students to build upon prior knowledge. When students can make sense of the material, they develop critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and analytical reasoning, all of which contribute to intellectual development (Tsunemoto, Trofimovich, Blanchet, Bertrand & Kennedy, 2022).

Significance on the Relationship between Instructional Predispositions of Teachers and Sense of Comprehensibility of Students

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.206 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students teachers is rejected.

Table III. Significance on the Relationship between Instructional Predispositions of Teachers and Sense of Comprehensibility of Students

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Instructional Predispositions of Teachers and Sense of Comprehensibility of Students	0.206	0.000	Reject

The result of the study is in congruence with the statement of Rand (2018) who stressed that education is most effective when it creates not only a transfer of knowledge but also an environment where students feel emotionally and cognitively supported. One essential psychological element in this process is the sense of comprehensibility, a student's perception that their learning experience is understandable, predictable, and structured. At the heart of nurturing this sense lies the instructional predispositions of teachers, which include their attitudes, values, teaching styles, and personal traits that influence how they engage with students and deliver instruction. There is a significant relationship between a teacher's instructional predispositions and how students perceive the comprehensibility of their educational experience.

This study is also supported by Yano, Kase & Oishi (2019) who argues that the relationship between instructional predispositions of teachers and the sense of comprehensibility of students is strong and deeply influential. Teachers who are naturally inclined to be clear, empathetic, structured, and emotionally intelligent create environments where students feel supported and capable of understanding their world. Strengthening this connection is essential for building not only academic success but also confident, self-aware, and motivated learners.

This is also aligned with the statement of Yıldız (2020) who said that collaborative and inclusive teaching practices further enhance the relationship between teacher predispositions and student comprehensibility. When teachers value student voices, encourage peer interaction, and build community, students are more likely to feel that their learning environment is logical and supportive. This social structure adds predictability and clarity to the classroom, reinforcing students' confidence in navigating academic challenges.

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a very high level of instructional predispositions of teachers. This means that the provisions relating to instructional predispositions of teachers is always manifested.

The study revealed a very high level of sense of comprehensibility of students. This indicates that the provisions relating to sense of comprehensibility of students are embodied in the item is always manifested.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship instructional predisposition of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students. This implies that the higher the level of instructional predisposition of teachers, the higher is the sense of comprehensibility of students. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between instructional predisposition of teachers and sense of comprehensibility of students was rejected.

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